

Cost and Punishment Proximity: Automated Dissection of Affective Decision-Making in Rodent Models

Project Report

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Certificate of Guide

To Whom It May Concern

This is to certify that Mr. Rahul Kedar Purnapatre from the 5th year of Integrated MSc. Biotechnology has completed work on the project entitled “**Cost and Punishment Proximity: Automated Dissection of Affective Decision-Making in Rodent Models**” in partial fulfilment of the course **IBT-723P**, from **December 2024 to April 2025** at the Centre for Neuroscience, Indian Institute of Science, Bengaluru, India, under the guidance of Dr. Anupama Sathyamurthy

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List of Abbreviations:

Abbreviation	Complete Form
ACC	Anterior Cingulate Cortex
AD	Advanced (as in Advanced vs. Delayed, from filename and context)
APP	Advanced Punishment Path
BLA	Basolateral Amygdala
CRs	Conditioned Fear Responses
CS	Conditioned Stimulus
CSV	Comma-Separated Value
DL	Delayed (as in Advanced vs. Delayed, from filename and context)
dIPFC	Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex
DPDT	Delayed Punishment Decision-making Task
DPP	Delayed Punishment Path
FCT	Forced Choice Trials
HPA	Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal (axis)
IR	Infrared (sensors)
NAc	Nucleus Accumbens
OFC	Orbitofrontal Cortex
PFC	Prefrontal Cortex

PWM	Prefrontal Cortex
RDT	Risky Decision-making Task
RL	Reinforcement Learning
R-O	Response-Outcome
ROI	Regions of Interest
SAM	Sympatho-Adreno-Medullary (axis)
TSI	Threat State/Value Integration (model)
US	Unconditioned Stimulus
vmPFC	Ventromedial Prefrontal Cortex
WT	Wild-Type (mice)

Cost and Punishment Proximity: Automated Dissection of Affective Decision-Making in Rodent Models

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Abstract

The timing of aversive outcomes critically shapes decision-making, yet how unavoidable punishment's proximity influences choice, unlike reward discounting, is less understood.

This thesis examines how mice choose between equal rewards when faced with immediate versus delayed inescapable punishment.

Using a validated automated T-maze, adult C57BL/6J mice (N=12) faced choices between two paths offering equal immediate rewards but differing in the timing (immediate/advanced vs. delayed) of an identical, unavoidable light stimulus, allowing precise behavioural recording without spatial bias. Mice robustly and significantly preferred the path leading to immediate (advanced) punishment. This "get it over with" strategy suggests the anticipatory cost of delayed punishment, potentially involving anxiety or dread, surpasses the immediate aversive impact.

Paradoxically, this preferred choice incurred significantly longer decision latencies at the choice point and increased overall trial durations. Such hesitation indicates substantial cognitive conflict when approaching an imminent, though ultimately preferred, negative outcome.

This study reveals a key dissociation between the factors driving ultimate choice preference (the imperative to minimise anticipatory cost) and the immediate cognitive processing costs incurred during decision execution (cognitive conflict). It offers a refined behavioural framework and a robust automated model for investigating the neural basis of decision-making under aversive conflict, holding implications for neuropsychiatric conditions where the evaluation of future negative consequences is perturbed.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 The Crucial Crossroads: Navigating the World Through Decisions

Life, in its essence, is a continuous series of choices. From trivial, such as deciding what to wear based on the morning's weather forecast or what to eat for breakfast, to the monumental, like choosing a career path, where to live, or selecting a life partner, decision-making is an extremely important and constant feature of our existence. Every day, people make countless choices which collectively steer the course of their lives. As an example, let's consider the daily commute: choosing a route might involve weighing speed against traffic, a simple decision with an impact on one's day. These choices are not passive selections but are active cognitive processes that allow us to navigate the complexities of our environment, pursue goals, and ultimately shape our lives (Korteling et al., 2023). The ability to effectively evaluate options and select an appropriate course of action is not merely a convenience but also a fundamental skill essential for survival. This also determines personal well-being and success in all facets of human endeavour. We see this in our daily lives, as an example, the professional realm, a manager's decision on resource allocation or a CEO's strategic choice can determine the fate of a project or an entire company and the livelihoods of its employees. The impact of these choices, both big and small, reverberates through our personal experiences and collectively influences societal progress and well-being (Ganuthula, 2024). Therefore, understanding the mechanisms that underpin our decisions is of utmost importance and offers us insight into how we learn, adapt, and thrive.

1.2 The Complexity of Decision-Making:

While making a decision might sometimes feel instantaneous or straightforward, the underlying neural architecture is extraordinarily complex and multifaceted. It is far more than a simple logical deduction; rather, it is an intricate interplay of various internal and external factors. Our emotions, for example, often play a significant, and sometimes overriding, role. The elation associated with a potential positive outcome or the fear of a negative consequence can heavily sway our choices, occasionally leading us away from the most rational path (Slovic et al., 2005). Consider a person choosing to invest in a high-risk

stock based on a "gut feeling" spurred by excitement, despite analytical data suggesting caution.

Furthermore, our past experiences and memories serve as a vast library of information that profoundly shapes our current decisions. If a particular choice led to a favourable outcome in the past, we are more likely to repeat it, and conversely, negative experiences can create strong aversions (Tulving & Craik, 2000). Think of a child who, after touching a hot stove, quickly learns to avoid similar objects in the future. This learning from experience is crucial for adapting our behaviour.

The landscape of decision-making is also frequently clouded by uncertainty. Rarely do we possess all the information needed to predict the outcome of our choices with absolute certainty. We constantly grapple with probabilities and potential risks, attempting to make the best possible choice with incomplete data (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979). A doctor deciding on the best treatment for a patient often weighs the potential benefits against the risks of side effects, based on statistical probabilities rather than guarantees. The cognitive load of evaluating multiple variables, potential future scenarios, and the inherent ambiguity of many situations highlights the sophisticated computational challenge our brains routinely solve when making decisions. This intricate dance of emotion, memory, and probabilistic reasoning makes the study of decision-making a rich and challenging field of inquiry.

1.3 Understanding Why Mice Model Our Choices

To unravel the intricate neural mechanisms governing such complex decision-making processes, scientists often turn to animal models. Among these, the laboratory mouse (*Mus musculus*) has emerged as a powerful and insightful tool. But why study the decision-making of a tiny rodent to understand our own elaborate choices? The answer lies in a fascinating intersection of behavioural parallels and conserved neurobiological architecture. Critically, many of the fundamental **factors and processes involved in decision-making, such as assessing risk, learning from consequences, and being driven by motivational states like hunger or fear, are not unique to humans but are also**

deeply embedded in the behavioural repertoire of so-called lower animals, including mice.

Consider a common scenario faced by both humans and mice: foraging for food when the rewards are uncertain. A person deciding which new restaurant to try, weighing the potential for a delightful meal against the risk of disappointment and wasted money, engages in a form of reward-based decision-making under uncertainty. Similarly, a mouse in a laboratory setting can be trained to choose between different levers or locations, each associated with a different probability or amount of a food reward (Carandini & Churchland, 2013). Researchers can observe how the mouse learns from previous choices, adapts its strategy when the reward contingencies change, and how factors like hunger influence its decisions. **Another illustrative example of this shared decision-making framework can be seen in how both species learn to avoid negative outcomes.** A human might learn to avoid a particular neighbourhood after a bad experience, weighing the convenience of a shortcut against the remembered sense of unease or a past negative event. In a parallel fashion, a mouse can learn to avoid a specific arm of a maze if it has previously encountered a mild, unpleasant stimulus there, such as a puff of air or a slight foot shock. In both instances, the decision to approach or avoid is shaped by past negative experiences and an assessment of potential risk versus reward, demonstrating a fundamental similarity in the adaptive decision-making process. The key observation is that both the human and the mouse, in these analogous situations, demonstrate an ability to weigh potential outcomes and adjust their behaviour based on experience to maximise rewards or minimise harm – a fundamental aspect of decision-making.

The true value of the mouse model becomes even clearer when we delve into the brain. Many of the fundamental brain structures and neural circuits involved in decision-making in humans have remarkably similar counterparts in the mouse brain. For instance, the prefrontal cortex (PFC) in humans is critically involved in higher-order cognitive functions, including planning, working memory, and inhibiting impulsive choices – all vital components of effective decision-making (Miller & Cohen, 2001). Neuroimaging studies in humans consistently show PFC activation when individuals are engaged in complex decision tasks. Remarkably, mice possess a homologous region, often referred to as the medial prefrontal cortex, which has been shown to be crucial for similar cognitive

functions, including flexible decision-making and adapting to changing rules (Euston, Gruber, & McNaughton, 2012).

Furthermore, structures like the basal ganglia, including the striatum, which are pivotal for learning from rewards and punishments (reinforcement learning) and habit formation in humans, are also highly conserved in mice and play analogous roles in their decision-making processes (Graybiel, 2008; Balleine & O'Doherty, 2010). The neurotransmitter systems, such as the dopamine system, which is essential for signalling reward prediction error and motivating behaviour in humans, operate in a strikingly similar fashion in the mouse brain (Schultz, Dayan, & Montague, 1997). This conservation of neural architecture and function allows researchers to use sophisticated genetic and neurophysiological tools in mice – tools that are often not applicable in human studies for ethical and practical reasons – to dissect the precise roles of specific genes, neurons, and circuits in the decision-making process. By studying these mechanisms in mice, we can gain invaluable insights into the fundamental principles that likely govern decision-making in our own brains, paving the way for a deeper understanding of both normal cognitive function and the dysregulations that can occur in various neurological and psychiatric disorders.

1.4 The Influence of Time: How Delay and Advancement Affect Choice

Beyond the inherent valence of potential outcomes, the timing of their occurrence exerts a powerful influence on decision-making. The phenomenon of **temporal discounting** describes the observation that the subjective value of an outcome decreases as the delay to its receipt increases (Ainslie, 1975; Critchfield & Kollins, 2001). This is most commonly studied in the context of rewards, where individuals often prefer smaller, immediate rewards over larger, delayed ones—a tendency linked to impulsivity and various maladaptive behaviours. For instance, a person might choose to receive \$50 today rather than \$100 in a year, even though the latter is objectively more valuable. This preference for immediate gratification highlights how delay diminishes the perceived worth of a future reward.

Conversely, the advancement of a reward can significantly increase its appeal. Imagine being told a much-anticipated vacation, originally scheduled for six months later, has been moved up to next month. The perceived value and excitement associated with the vacation would likely surge.

While extensively studied for rewards, the role of temporal factors in modulating the impact of aversive outcomes is less understood, and findings have been less consistent (Liley et al., 2019; Orsini et al., 2016). Intuitively, a delayed punishment might be perceived as less costly than an immediate one, mirroring the discounting observed for rewards. According to this "aversive discounting" perspective, organisms might be expected to tolerate a delayed punishment more readily than an immediate one of equal magnitude. For example, a student might prefer a detention scheduled for next week over one scheduled for immediately after school, even if the duration is the same. However, this simple extrapolation may overlook crucial psychological factors associated with waiting for an unpleasant event, such as the dread or anxiety that can build over time. Similarly, if an unpleasant task, like a dental appointment, is unexpectedly moved to an earlier date, the immediate displeasure might be high, but it also curtails the period of anxious anticipation. The interplay between the immediacy of the negative event and the duration of any preceding anxiety makes the impact of timing on aversive choices complex.

1.5 Punishment Timing: Specific Focus of the Thesis - Immediate vs. Delayed Consequences in an Avoidance Paradigm

The period preceding an anticipated aversive event can itself be a source of significant negative utility, often characterized by states of anxiety, stress, or dread (Berns et al., 2006; Leknes et al., 2011). The anticipation of a future negative outcome can generate a sustained state of physiological arousal and negative affect that organisms may seek to terminate, even if it means confronting the punishment sooner. This contrasts with the simple aversive discounting view (discussed in Section 1.3) and suggests an alternative hypothesis based on "utility from anticipation," where the negative experience of waiting makes the delayed

punishment more aversive overall than the immediate one, potentially leading individuals to choose options that hasten the unpleasant event to "get it over with."

This thesis specifically investigates this nuanced interplay by examining how rodents make choices when faced with different timings of a mild aversive stimulus (e.g., a bright light or a puff of air) in a controlled decision-making task. The central question is: **Under what conditions, and to what extent, do rats prefer to expedite an unavoidable aversive event rather than endure a period of anticipation for a delayed one?**

For example, in our experimental setup, a rat might be presented with a choice between two arms of a T-maze. Choosing one arm leads to the exposure of an advanced aversive stimulus. Choosing the other arm leads to the delayed aversive stimulus (varying led positions in each arm), during which the rat must wait in a specific location.

- If simple aversive discounting dominates, we would expect rats to consistently choose the delayed aversive stimulus, as its perceived cost would be lower.
- However, if the anxiety or stress of anticipating the delayed stimulus is significant, rats might instead show a preference for the arm leading to the immediate aversive stimulus, thereby escaping the period of waiting.

By systematically varying the duration of the delay, placement and potentially the intensity of the aversive stimulus, this research aims to delineate the conditions under which the "desire to get it over with" outweighs the tendency to devalue delayed negative outcomes.

Understanding this trade-off is crucial for a more complete model of decision-making under aversive conditions, with implications for understanding anxiety disorders where anticipatory stress plays a significant role.

1.6 The Rationale for Automation: Enhancing Precision and Efficiency in Behavioural Assays

The study of decision-making, particularly involving nuanced choices like those between immediate and delayed aversive stimuli, demands high precision, consistency, and the

ability to collect substantial amounts of data. Traditional manual methods for conducting behavioural assays, such as T-maze tasks, are often labour-intensive, prone to human error, and can introduce variability that obscures subtle but significant behavioural effects.

The importance and need for automation in this context are multifaceted:

1. **Consistency and Standardisation:** Automated systems ensure that every trial is conducted in exactly the same way. This includes the precise timing of stimulus presentation (e.g., onset of cues, delivery of aversive stimuli, duration of delays), the recording of choices, and the inter-trial intervals. Such standardisation minimises variability introduced by human experimenters, whose handling, timing, and even subtle cues can unintentionally influence animal behaviour. For example, an automated T-maze ensures that the opening of a gate, the presentation of a light cue, or the delivery of an air puff occurs with millisecond accuracy for every animal across all trials, something virtually impossible to achieve manually.
2. **Reduced Experimenter Bias:** Automation removes the direct interaction between the experimenter and the animal during the critical phases of the task. This eliminates the possibility of experimenter bias, where the researcher's expectations or unconscious cues might influence the animal's choices.
3. **Increased Throughput and Efficiency:** Automated systems can run experiments continuously or with minimal supervision, allowing for the collection of large datasets more rapidly than manual methods. This is particularly important for studies requiring many trials per subject or large numbers of subjects to achieve sufficient statistical power, as is often the case in behavioural neuroscience. An automated T-maze can run multiple animals sequentially or in parallel (if multiple mazes are used) with programmed protocols, freeing up researcher time for data analysis and other tasks.
4. **Precise Data Logging:** Automated assays provide accurate and objective recording of behavioural parameters. This includes not just the final choice (e.g., left or right arm) but also latencies to make a choice, time spent in different zones of the maze, and other subtle behavioural measures that might be difficult or impossible to capture reliably by human observation. This detailed, timestamped data is crucial for a thorough analysis of decision-making processes.

5. **Minimising Animal Stress:** While the aversive stimuli are an integral part of the study, automation can help minimise extraneous stress to the animals. Consistent handling protocols (often reduced with automation) and a predictable experimental environment can lead to more stable and reliable behavioural readouts.

Given the specific aims of this thesis—to dissect the preferences between immediate and delayed aversive outcomes where subtle differences in timing and anticipation are critical—an **automated T-maze assay** is employed. This approach allows for the rigorous control over temporal parameters and the objective collection of choice data necessary to address the research questions with the highest possible degree of accuracy and reliability.

1.7 Research Question: Advanced vs. Delayed Punishment Selection in Mice

Given the background highlighting the complexities of approach-avoidance conflict and the modulatory role of time, particularly the potentially high cost of anticipating negative outcomes, this thesis addresses a specific gap in our understanding: **How do mice evaluate and choose between options leading to equivalent rewards but differing in the temporal proximity of an associated punishment (immediate/advanced vs. delayed)?** By employing a purpose-built automated T-maze, this study investigates whether the principles of simple aversive discounting hold, or if the anticipated cost of waiting for a delayed punishment drives preference towards confronting the punishment sooner.

CHAPTER 2
LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Frameworks of Decision-Making

Decision-making, the cognitive process of selecting a course of action among multiple alternatives, is governed by evaluating the potential outcomes associated with each option. Classical economic theories, such as Expected Utility Theory, posit that rational agents choose the option that maximizes their expected subjective utility, integrating the value and probability of potential outcomes (von Neumann & Morgenstern, 1944). This framework assumes consistent preferences and the ability to assign a cardinal utility value to diverse outcomes. However, behavioural economics has demonstrated systematic deviations from pure rationality, highlighting the influence of cognitive biases and heuristics (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974). Prospect Theory, for instance, modified expected utility by incorporating reference dependence, loss aversion, and non-linear weighting of probabilities, providing a psychologically more realistic account of choice under risk (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979).

From a computational neuroscience perspective, Reinforcement Learning (RL) offers a powerful framework for understanding how organisms learn from rewards and punishments to optimize behaviour (Sutton & Barto, 1998). Central to many RL models and decision theories is the concept of subjective value – a common neural currency that allows for the comparison of disparate options, integrating multiple attributes (e.g., magnitude, probability, delay, effort) into a single measure of desirability or utility. Evidence suggests that brain regions like the ventromedial prefrontal cortex (vmPFC), particularly the orbitofrontal cortex (OFC), and associated parts of the striatum play a crucial role in computing and representing these subjective values, effectively encoding the 'decision utility' of available options (Padoa-Schioppa & Assad, 2006; Levy & Glimcher, 2012). The selection process itself, choosing the highest-valued option, may then involve lateral prefrontal and parietal areas.

However, choice is not solely driven by rational calculation or explicit value comparison. Pavlovian processes, which link stimuli innately or through learning to approach or withdrawal responses, can exert a strong influence on instrumental behaviour (Dayan et al., 2006). For instance, cues predicting immediate rewards can potentiate approach behaviour and interfere with inhibition, potentially contributing to impulsive choices even when a delayed option is objectively more valuable (Guitart-Masip et al., 2012). Furthermore, the

specific decision strategy employed can vary based on factors like task complexity, time pressure, cognitive load, expertise, and individual traits (e.g., need for cognition). Organisms might shift between comprehensive, compensatory strategies (weighing all attributes) and simpler, non-compensatory heuristics (focusing on key attributes) depending on the context.

2.2 Rational Choice and Its Limitations

The classical model of decision-making rests on the Rational Choice Theory (RCT), which assumes that individuals act as utility maximisers, making decisions based on consistent preferences and complete information (Von Neumann & Morgenstern, 1944). According to this model, decisions are the outcome of logical deliberation where the agent evaluates all available options and selects the one with the highest expected utility.

While RCT provides a foundational framework, its explanatory power is limited when applied to real-world scenarios where cognitive constraints, emotional fluctuations, and contextual ambiguities interfere with rational deliberation. Empirical findings in psychology and behavioural economics have revealed persistent violations of rationality, including preference reversals, inconsistency over time, and context-dependent valuation (Tversky & Kahneman, 1986). For instance, individuals often exhibit dynamic inconsistency—preferring one option in the future and a different one when the moment of choice arrives—something RCT fails to predict (Laibson, 1997).

The assumption of stable preferences is particularly challenged in emotionally charged or time-sensitive decisions, where factors like stress, impulsivity, and uncertainty degrade the quality of deliberation. In such cases, decision-makers frequently rely on heuristics—mental shortcuts that bypass formal computation but often lead to systematic errors (Gigerenzer & Gaissmaier, 2011). These limitations necessitate the development of alternative models that better reflect the nuanced ways in which humans evaluate outcomes and make choices.

2.3 Punishment and Aversive Learning: Behavioural Paradigms

The capacity to learn about the adverse consequences of actions and modify behaviour accordingly is fundamental to adaptive functioning. Within the framework of learning theory, **punishment** refers specifically to an instrumental or operant process whereby the contingent delivery of an aversive outcome following a specific behaviour leads to a decrease in the future probability or frequency of that behaviour (Skinner, 1938; Azrin & Holz, 1966). It is crucial to distinguish this precise definition from related, yet distinct, forms of aversive learning (Jean-Richard-Dit-Bressel et al., 2018).

Punishment involves a **response-outcome (R-O) contingency** where the action causes the aversive event. This contrasts sharply with **Pavlovian (classical) fear conditioning**, where an aversive unconditioned stimulus (US, e.g., shock) is paired with a neutral conditioned stimulus (CS, e.g., tone), rendering the CS capable of eliciting conditioned fear responses (CRs, e.g., freezing) regardless of the animal's behaviour (i.e., a stimulus-outcome or S-O contingency) (LeDoux, 2000; Maren, 2001). While conditioned fear can suppress ongoing appetitive behaviours (conditioned suppression), this behavioural reduction stems from the predictive value of the CS, not from a direct contingency between the suppressed behaviour and the US. Punishment is also fundamentally different from **negative reinforcement**, which encompasses **escape learning** (behaviour increases because it terminates an ongoing aversive stimulus) and **active avoidance learning** (behaviour increases because it prevents the occurrence of an anticipated aversive stimulus). Thus, punishment uniquely serves to suppress specific actions due to their learned adverse consequences.

Laboratory studies of punishment employ various paradigms and aversive stimuli. Punishment procedures can be broadly categorized as **positive punishment**, where an aversive stimulus is presented contingent upon a response (e.g., pressing a lever delivers a shock), or **negative punishment** (also known as omission training or response cost), where an appetitive stimulus or access to reinforcement is removed contingent upon a response (e.g., pressing a lever removes access to food). The majority of research investigating the neurobiology of punishment and the paradigms relevant to this thesis utilize positive punishment procedures.

A variety of stimuli serve as effective positive punishers in rodent research. **Electric footshock** remains widely used due to its precise control over intensity, duration, and timing, allowing for parametric manipulation (Fanselow, 1984). However, ethical considerations and regulatory guidelines increasingly encourage minimizing pain-inducing stimuli. Consequently, alternative punishers have gained prominence, including **air puffs** directed at the animal, **loud broadband noise**, or species-specific **ultrasonic vocalizations** associated with distress. For studies involving consumption, adulterating palatable solutions (e.g., sucrose) with bitter compounds like **quinine** serves as an effective punisher. Relevant to the methodology employed in this thesis, **exposure to bright light** leverages the innate aversion of nocturnal rodents to intensely illuminated environments and has emerged as an effective, non-invasive punisher in decision-making and conflict tasks (File & Hyde, 1978)

The effectiveness of punishment is influenced by several factors, including punisher intensity (more intense punishers produce greater suppression), immediacy (punishment delivered immediately after the response is far more effective than delayed punishment – a key principle explored in this thesis), schedule (continuous punishment is generally more effective initially than intermittent punishment), motivation for the punished response, and the availability of alternative, unpunished responses that can achieve the same goal (Azrin & Holz, 1966; Camp et al., 1967).

Beyond simple response suppression, punishment plays a critical role in shaping **decision-making**, particularly in situations involving conflict between potential rewards and punishments. Several behavioural paradigms have been developed to specifically investigate these processes in rodents:

1. **Punished Reward Tasks:** These tasks often involve training an animal to perform a response for a reward (e.g., lever pressing for food pellets) and then introducing a punishment contingency for the same response (e.g., each lever press now yields both food and a shock). The degree to which the animal suppresses its responding provides a measure of the punishment's impact relative to the reward's value. Variations might involve offering two levers, one delivering only reward and the other delivering reward plus punishment, to directly assess choice.

2. **Risky Decision-making Task (RDT):** This paradigm models choices involving risk, typically offering a selection between a small, certain ("safe") reward and a larger reward associated with a probability of receiving punishment (Simon et al., 2009). By varying the probability of punishment across blocks or sessions, researchers can assess an individual's sensitivity to risk and preference for larger, uncertain gains versus smaller, certain ones. This task has proven valuable for studying decision-making deficits in models of addiction and other disorders.
3. **Delayed Punishment Decision-making Task (DPDT):** This task, highly pertinent to the current study, directly investigates the influence of temporal delay on punishment efficacy within a choice context (Liley et al., 2019). Animals typically choose between a small, safe reward and a larger reward associated with a guaranteed punishment. Critically, the delay between the choice/reward delivery and the onset of the punishment is systematically varied. This allows for the assessment of "delayed punishment discounting," or how the subjective impact of the punishment diminishes as its temporal distance from the choice increases. This paradigm provides a direct behavioural readout of sensitivity to the temporal proximity of adverse consequences. The T-maze task employed in this thesis adapts this core principle by comparing choices when punishment is either immediate (advanced) or explicitly delayed, while keeping reward parameters constant.
4. **Effort-Based Decision Tasks:** While not involving direct application of an aversive stimulus like shock or light, tasks requiring animals to choose between high-reward/high-effort options and low-reward/low-effort options tap into related cost-benefit computations (Salamone et al., 2007). The effort requirement (e.g., climbing a barrier, performing many lever presses) acts as a cost that is weighed against the potential reward, analogous in some ways to how punishment cost is evaluated. T-maze configurations are frequently used for these paradigms as well.

The study of punishment encompasses a range of behavioural paradigms designed to understand how organisms learn from and respond to response-contingent aversive outcomes. Distinguishing punishment from related forms of aversive learning like fear conditioning and avoidance is crucial for accurate interpretation. Paradigms specifically designed to embed punishment within a decision-making context, such as the RDT and

DPDT, allow for investigation into how punishment probability and delay interact with reward value to guide choice behaviour. The DPDT, and related tasks manipulating the temporal proximity of punishment as used in this thesis, are particularly valuable for dissecting the interplay between immediate aversion, delayed consequences, and anticipatory states in shaping adaptive (and maladaptive) decisions.

2.4 Temporal Discounting of Aversive Outcomes

A cornerstone concept in the study of intertemporal choice is **temporal discounting**, the principle that the subjective value or impact of future outcomes diminishes as the delay to their occurrence increases (Ainslie, 1975; Frederick et al., 2002). This phenomenon is robustly documented for rewards, where individuals across species frequently prefer smaller, immediate rewards over objectively larger rewards available only after a delay (Kirby et al., 1999; Green & Myerson, 2004). Steeper discounting of future rewards is often associated with impulsivity and is implicated in various clinical conditions, including addiction and attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (Bickel et al., 2014). Mathematically, this decline in value is often best described by hyperbolic or related functions, indicating a disproportionately sharp decrease in value for delays occurring sooner rather than later (Green & Myerson, 1996).

Extrapolating from the domain of rewards, a parallel principle might be expected to govern the evaluation of future punishments: **aversive temporal discounting**. This view posits that the subjective aversiveness or deterrent effect of a punishment should decrease as the delay to its delivery increases (Mischel et al., 1969). Consequently, organisms might be expected to tolerate, or be less deterred by, punishments scheduled to occur further in the future compared to identical punishments delivered immediately following a choice or action. Support for this perspective comes from early studies showing diminished behavioural control exerted by delayed punishments in humans (Banks & Vogel-Sprott, 1965). More recently, rodent studies using the Delayed Punishment Decision-making Task (DPDT) have provided compelling evidence consistent with aversive discounting. In these tasks, rats often increase their preference for larger, punished rewards as the delay between choosing that reward and receiving the guaranteed punishment (e.g., footshock) is

systematically lengthened (Liley et al., 2019; Orsini et al., 2021). This pattern suggests that the perceived negative value of the shock diminishes with temporal distance, making the larger reward option more attractive despite the inevitable consequence. Such discounting of future negative outcomes offers a potential explanation for maladaptive decision patterns where individuals persistently choose options with immediate benefits despite predictable, yet delayed, adverse consequences (Bechara et al., 2002).

However, the notion that aversive outcomes are discounted simply in parallel with rewards has been challenged by a body of conflicting findings, suggesting a more complex interplay between time and aversion. Unlike the generally consistent preference for immediate rewards, humans sometimes exhibit a preference for experiencing unpleasant events sooner rather than later (Loewenstein, 1987; Berns et al., 2006). For instance, individuals might prefer to receive a painful electric shock immediately rather than wait for it, even if the intensity is identical (Berns et al., 2006). This phenomenon, often attributed to the negative utility derived from dread or anticipation (discussed further in Section 2.4), directly contradicts the prediction of simple aversive discounting. Similarly, studies examining intertemporal choices involving losses or punishments have sometimes found shallower discounting rates compared to rewards, or even negative discounting (preference for immediacy) under certain conditions (Thaler, 1981; MacKeigan et al., 1993)

Research in non-human animals also reveals complexities. While the DPDT results from Liley et al. (2019) support discounting, a recent study by Vanderveldt & Rachlin (2023) using a T-maze task with choices between differently timed shocks and rewards found little support for either simple aversive discounting or a strong negative utility from anticipation (dread). Instead, their findings were more consistent with a model where shocks exert time-dependent negative spill-over effects on the perceived value of subsequent rewards, suggesting intricate interactions between appetitive and aversive processing across time rather than independent discounting functions.

Several factors likely contribute to these divergent findings and the overall complexity of temporal processing for aversive outcomes:

- **Anticipatory Affect:** As mentioned, the aversive experience of waiting (dread, anxiety) can generate its own negative utility, potentially counteracting or

exceeding the discounting effect of delay itself, thus driving preference towards immediate resolution (Berns et al., 2006).

- **Framing Effects:** How temporal information is presented significantly impacts choice. The "date/delay effect" demonstrates that framing future outcomes using specific calendar dates (e.g., "receive shock on May 10th") leads to less steep discounting (i.e., greater consideration of the future outcome) compared to framing using equivalent delay intervals (e.g., "receive shock in 5 days") (Read et al., 2005; LeBoeuf, 2006). This may occur because dates evoke more concrete, episodic future thinking, reducing the psychological distance compared to abstract delay intervals.
- **Outcome Type and Magnitude:** The specific nature and intensity of the punishment likely influence discounting rates. Different neural and psychological processes may be engaged when discounting physical pain versus monetary loss versus social rejection, for example. Magnitude effects, well-documented for rewards (larger rewards discounted less steeply), may also apply non-linearly to punishments.
- **Individual Differences:** Significant variability exists between individuals in how they discount future outcomes. Traits like impulsivity, anxiety levels, stress perception, age, and sex can influence discounting rates for both rewards and punishments (Lempert et al., 2012). Notably, Liley et al. (2019) reported sex differences in rats, with males discounting delayed punishment more steeply than females.
- **Interaction with Reward Context:** As suggested by Vanderveldt & Rachlin (2023), the timing of punishment relative to associated or subsequent rewards may be critical. A punishment occurring close in time to a reward might devalue that reward more strongly than a temporally distant punishment, influencing choice independently of the punishment's intrinsic discounted value.

The inherent complexity and context-dependency observed in the temporal evaluation of aversive outcomes highlight the limitations of applying a simple reward-discounting framework directly to punishment. The present study aims to contribute clarity by examining a specific scenario within this complex landscape. By using an automated T-maze to present mice with a direct choice between pathways offering identical, immediate rewards but differing only in the timing of a guaranteed punishment (immediate/advanced vs. delayed bright light exposure), we seek to isolate the influence of punishment timing under controlled conditions. This design allows for a direct assessment of whether behaviour is primarily driven by the discounting of the delayed punishment's intrinsic aversion or by the potential cost associated with anticipating its delayed arrival.

2.5 The Psychology of Anticipation and Delay: Anxiety, Stress, and Dread

The temporal distance to an event does not merely scale its perceived magnitude; the intervening period, the time spent waiting, is itself imbued with psychological significance that profoundly shapes valuation and choice, particularly when the anticipated event is aversive. While simple discounting models (discussed in Section 2.3) predict that delayed punishments should be less impactful, they often fail to account for the potentially substantial negative utility generated by the very act of anticipating an unpleasant future outcome (Loewenstein, 1987; Berns et al., 2006). Understanding the affective states elicited during this delay period – primarily **anticipatory anxiety**, **stress**, and **dread** – is crucial for explaining behaviours that deviate from straightforward discounting predictions, such as the preference for immediate punishment observed in some studies and central to the findings of this thesis.

Anticipatory anxiety is fundamentally a future-oriented emotional state, characterized by apprehension, worry, and heightened vigilance concerning potential future threats or negative events (Grupe & Nitschke, 2013). Unlike fear, which is typically considered a response to imminent, identifiable danger, anxiety relates more to uncertain or temporally distant threats. This state involves distinct cognitive components, such as repetitive negative thoughts about potential outcomes and one's ability to cope, and significant

physiological components, including activation of the autonomic nervous system (e.g., increased heart rate, skin conductance) driven by the body's stress response systems. The anticipation of a guaranteed, albeit delayed, punishment fits squarely within this framework, acting as a potent psychological **stressor**. The impending negative event triggers physiological stress responses via the sympatho-adreno-medullary (SAM) axis and the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis, preparing the organism for potential challenge but also contributing to a sustained state of unpleasant arousal (Ulrich-Lai & Herman, 2009).

Dread represents a specific facet of this negative anticipation, defined as the preference for an unpleasant event to occur sooner rather than later (Berns et al., 2006; Loewenstein, 1987). It reflects a strong desire to resolve the uncertainty and terminate the aversive state of waiting, even at the cost of immediate suffering. Neuroimaging studies in humans have linked the experience of dread to activity in brain regions associated with negative affect and interoception, such as the insula and anterior cingulate cortex (ACC), suggesting that the subjective feeling of waiting for something bad is actively encoded and contributes significantly to decision utility (Berns et al., 2006; Leknes et al., 2011).

Crucially, the subjective experience of anticipatory anxiety, stress, and dread constitutes a significant **psychological cost of waiting**. This cost is not captured by models that only consider the discounted value of the future punishment itself. When faced with a choice between an immediate punishment and a delayed one, the decision-maker is effectively comparing the cost of the immediate aversive event against the combined cost of the delayed aversive event plus the integrated cost of the aversive anticipatory state during the delay period (Loewenstein, 1987). If the cost of anticipation is sufficiently high, the overall subjective burden of the delayed punishment pathway can exceed that of the immediate punishment pathway, leading to the seemingly paradoxical choice to "get it over with".

The affective and physiological states associated with anticipation can further influence decision-making through several mechanisms:

1. **Biased Valuation:** Acute stress and anxiety can alter how potential outcomes are evaluated. Stress can impair the processing of reward information and potentially amplify the perceived negativity of uncertain or future threats (Mather & Lighthall, 2012; Robinson et al., 2013). The sustained negative state during anticipation might

'contaminate' the evaluation of the entire delayed option, making it less appealing overall.

2. **Altered Decision Strategies:** Stress exposure has been shown to bias behaviour away from flexible, goal-directed control towards more rigid, habitual response patterns (Schwabe & Wolf, 2011). In the context of temporal choice, this could manifest as a preference for immediate resolution (either reward or punishment) rather than engaging in more complex deliberation about future outcomes. High arousal states associated with anxiety may also narrow attentional focus, leading to reliance on simpler heuristics.
3. **Modulation of Temporal Discounting:** While the direct effects of acute stress on delay discounting rates have yielded mixed results in humans (potentially depending on individual differences in stress appraisal and the nature of the stressor) (Lempert et al., 2012), the drive to escape the aversive state of anticipation might functionally increase the preference for immediate outcomes, irrespective of changes in the formal discounting rate.
4. **Influence of Bodily States:** The physiological arousal accompanying anticipation (e.g., changes in heart rate, electrodermal activity) is not merely an epiphenomenon but can feed back to influence cognitive processing and decision biases (Critchley, 2005). Models like the Threat State/Value Integration (TSI) model explicitly propose that threat-induced autonomic states modulate the valuation of competing incentives during approach-avoidance decisions (Pittig et al., 2021).

Therefore, the psychological and physiological impact of anticipating a delayed punishment provides a compelling theoretical framework for understanding why organisms might choose to face an aversive consequence immediately. The preference for the advanced punishment path observed in the current study strongly suggests that, under these specific experimental conditions (guaranteed punishment, immediate reward), the integrated cost associated with the delay period – the anxiety, stress, and/or dread of waiting – surpasses the perceived cost of the immediate, albeit identical, punishment. This interpretation shifts the focus from simply discounting the future punishment to actively avoiding the aversive state of anticipation itself.

2.6 Neural Correlates of Decision-Making, Punishment, Conflict, and Temporal Processing

Understanding the complex decisions investigated requires examining the interplay between several key brain circuits involved in evaluating situations, handling punishment, managing conflict, and processing time.

The amygdala plays a critical role, particularly in processing the emotional significance of events, especially negative stimuli and threats. It is fundamental for learning and expressing fear responses, like those seen in Pavlovian conditioning. Specifically, the basolateral amygdala (BLA) is important for learning from actions that lead to punishment. Overactivity in the amygdala is often seen in anxiety disorders when individuals respond to cues associated with threats. Through its connections with the prefrontal cortex and striatum, the amygdala influences how we calculate value and choose actions, especially when potential threat or loss is involved.

Higher-level cognitive functions, such as decision-making, planning, and controlling behavior, are orchestrated by the prefrontal cortex (PFC). Different areas within the PFC have distinct roles. The orbitofrontal cortex (OFC) and ventromedial PFC (vmPFC), for example, are crucial for representing the anticipated subjective value of outcomes and integrating sensory input with our internal states to guide choices. The OFC, in particular, seems necessary for adjusting behavior when the value of outcomes changes and is implicated in how we process delayed punishment. The dorsolateral PFC (dlPFC) is more involved in executive functions like working memory and strategic planning, including resolving conflicts between different response options during decision-making. Another significant region, the anterior cingulate cortex (ACC), often considered part of the medial PFC, is heavily involved in monitoring for conflicts, detecting errors, assessing the costs of actions, and signaling when cognitive control needs to be adjusted. ACC activity often increases during tasks involving approach-avoidance conflicts.

The striatum, a major part of the basal ganglia, is central to selecting actions, forming habits, and processing reward and punishment signals, a process significantly modulated by dopamine. Within the striatum, the ventral portion, which includes the nucleus accumbens (NAc), is key to motivation, driving the pursuit of rewards ('wanting'), and

energizing behavior, especially when overcoming effort is required. The dorsal striatum is more linked to learning habits based on stimulus-response associations. The caudate nucleus, part of the dorsal striatum, has been specifically identified as playing a role in choices made during approach-avoidance conflicts.

Finally, the insula is involved in interoception – the sensing of internal bodily states. It represents subjective feelings and processes risk and uncertainty by integrating visceral sensory information with emotional and cognitive functions. Heightened insula activation is observed during unpleasant experiences and is characteristic of anxiety disorders, potentially contributing to the subjective feelings of dread or anxiety. Insula activity is also frequently noted during approach-avoidance conflict situations.

Decisions involving temporally distinct punishments likely engage this distributed network. Evaluating the immediate versus delayed punishment involves value computations (OFC/vmPFC, striatum), processing of aversive signals (amygdala, insula), potentially monitoring conflict (ACC), and considering the temporal dimension, the neural basis of which is still being elucidated but likely involves interactions between these core decision circuits and regions involved in time perception.

2.7 Automated Behavioural Assays in Neuroscience Research

The study of behaviour in animal models is fundamental to neuroscience, providing the ultimate readout for assessing the function of genes, circuits, and pharmacological manipulations. However, behaviour is inherently complex and sensitive to numerous environmental variables, posing significant challenges for achieving objectivity, reproducibility, and high resolution in experimental measurements (Crabbe et al., 1999; Wahlsten, 2001). Traditional behavioural testing often relies heavily on manual observation, scoring, and handling by human experimenters. While indispensable in the history of the field, these methods are susceptible to limitations including observer bias, inter-experimenter variability, the confounding effects of handling stress on animal physiology and behaviour, and constraints on the complexity and duration of experimental

protocols (Lewejohann et al., 2006; Balcombe et al., 2004). Furthermore, manual methods often lack the temporal and spatial precision required to capture subtle but potentially important aspects of behavioural performance.

The increasing demand for more rigorous, reliable, and scalable behavioural data has driven the development and adoption of **automated behavioural assays** (Tecott & Nestler, 2004; Spruijt & DeVisser, 2006). These systems utilize technology – encompassing sensors (e.g., infrared beams, video cameras, touchscreens, force plates), actuators (e.g., motorized doors, levers, stimulus lights, automated feeders/pumps), and computer control – to administer behavioural tasks and record data with minimal direct human intervention during the testing phase. The advantages offered by automation are substantial and address many limitations of manual approaches.

Automation enforces strict adherence to experimental protocols. The timing of events, presentation of stimuli, delivery of rewards or punishments, and control of environmental parameters are precisely managed by the control system, ensuring consistency across trials, subjects, and even different laboratories (Richardson, 2015). This standardization is critical for reducing experimental noise and improving the reproducibility of behavioural findings, a persistent challenge in the field. Standardizing training protocols via automation can also reduce variability arising from differing training histories (Calapai et al., 2017). Also by removing the need for manual scoring during the task, automation eliminates subjective judgments and potential biases (conscious or unconscious) introduced by human observers. Data acquisition is based on objective sensor readings or algorithmic analysis of video feeds and not only reduces variability due to biases but also reduces the bulk of the workload.

Reducing or eliminating the need for experimenters to handle animals immediately before or during testing significantly minimizes stress, which is known to profoundly impact performance on various cognitive and affective tasks, including decision-making and learning (Balcombe et al., 2004; Hurst & West, 2010). This allows for assessment of behaviour in a more naturalistic or less perturbed state.

Automated systems can capture behavioural data with high temporal and spatial resolution. Sensors like infrared beams can log precise event times (e.g., crossing a threshold, making a choice), while video tracking systems coupled with deep-learning algorithms can provide

detailed information (e.g., gait, velocity, acceleration, posture, specific action patterns) that are often inaccessible through manual scoring. This richness of data allows for more nuanced analyses of behavioural strategies and performance.

Automated setups can often run multiple animals in parallel or conduct experiments over extended periods (e.g., overnight or across several days within home-cage environments) without continuous experimenter supervision, significantly increasing experimental throughput and allowing for the collection of larger datasets. Automation makes it feasible to implement intricate behavioural paradigms involving complex conditional logic, precise timing of multiple events, adaptive adjustments based on performance, or long sequences of trials that would be extremely difficult or error-prone to administer manually.

The **T-maze**, a staple apparatus for studying spatial learning, memory, and decision-making, has particularly benefited from automation. Automated T-mazes typically incorporate sensors (e.g., infrared beams, pressure plates, video tracking) to detect the animal's position at the start arm, choice point, and within the goal arms. Automated doors (often guillotine-style operated by servos) control access to different sections of the maze, allowing for forced-choice trials, imposition of delays, or prevention of retracing. Reward delivery (liquid rewards via solenoid valves) and stimulus presentation (e.g., cue lights) within the goal arms are triggered automatically based on the animal's location and the programmed task logic. Modifications like continuous loops or return arms allow animals to initiate subsequent trials autonomously, further reducing handling and enabling the collection of many trials within a session.

The automated T-maze system developed and utilized in the present thesis embodies these principles to specifically address the research question concerning advanced versus delayed punishment. Automation was deemed crucial for the precise execution and objective measurement required. The system integrated multiple infrared sensors to accurately track the mouse's progression through defined regions of interest (ROIs), triggering specific events. Servo-controlled doors regulated access to choice arms and prevented retracing based on sensor input and task phase. Automated delivery of rewards (via solenoid valves) and the aversive light stimulus (via controlled LED panels) ensured consistent and precisely timed consequences contingent on the animal's choice. The entire sequence was orchestrated by a microcontroller executing custom logic, ensuring consistent trial structure

from initiation (triggered by ROI1 sensor) through choice registration (ROI2/ROI3), consequence delivery, and trial reset. This automated approach minimized experimenter intervention during trials, enabled high-resolution logging of choice and timing data via serial communication, and ultimately provided a robust platform for investigating the nuances of decision-making under temporal punishment conflict.

By enhancing standardization, objectivity, precision, and efficiency, while minimizing stress confounds, these systems provide higher quality, more reliable data for understanding the neural basis of behaviour. The successful implementation of the automated T-maze described herein was essential for rigorously testing the hypotheses regarding choice preference between immediate and delayed punishments. While automation itself does not guarantee valid conclusions – careful experimental design and interpretation remain paramount – it provides an indispensable tool for tackling complex behavioural questions with the necessary precision and control.

2.8 Gaps in Current Knowledge and Rationale for the Present Study

The preceding review has shown our current understanding of decision-making under conditions involving punishment, with a particular focus on the influence of temporal factors. It is clear that choices are guided by complex computations integrating reward value, punishment cost, effort, probability, and delay. Foundational theories from economics, psychology, and reinforcement learning provide frameworks for understanding these processes, while advances in behavioural neuroscience have begun to delineate the underlying neural circuitry involving key structures like the prefrontal cortex, amygdala, striatum, and insula, modulated by neurotransmitter systems including dopamine and serotonin. Furthermore, methodological advancements, particularly the adoption of automated behavioural assays, have significantly enhanced the precision and reliability of research in this domain.

Despite this progress, critical gaps remain in our knowledge, particularly concerning how organisms evaluate and choose between options involving temporally distinct aversive

outcomes. This review has highlighted several key areas where further investigation is warranted:

1. **Ambiguity in Temporal Preference for Punishment:** A major unresolved issue is the lack of consensus regarding whether organisms consistently discount delayed punishments (i.e., prefer them over immediate ones) or if other factors, such as the aversive nature of anticipation, can lead to a preference for immediate punishment. As discussed (Section 2.3), findings are inconsistent across studies in both humans and animals, suggesting that the operative principle is highly context-dependent and not fully captured by simple extrapolation from reward discounting models (Berns et al., 2006; Liley et al., 2019; Vanderveldt & Rachlin, 2023).
2. **Isolation of Punishment Timing Effects:** Many previous studies examining temporal aspects of punishment have involved concurrent variations in other parameters, such as reward timing or magnitude, making it difficult to definitively attribute observed choice patterns solely to the manipulation of punishment delay. There is a need for paradigms that carefully control associated rewards and punishment characteristics to specifically isolate the impact of the temporal proximity of the aversive event itself.
3. **Behavioural Quantification of Anticipatory Cost vs. Discounting:** While the psychological cost of waiting for an aversive event (anticipatory anxiety or dread, Section 2.4) provides a strong theoretical explanation for preferring immediate punishment, direct behavioural evidence quantifying this cost relative to the discounted value of the punishment in animal models is limited. Establishing behavioural paradigms that can dissociate these factors is crucial.
4. **Neural Mechanisms of Immediate vs. Delayed Punishment Choice:** Although the neural circuits involved in processing reward, punishment, conflict, and time are broadly identified (Section 2.5), the specific neural computations and dynamic interactions within these circuits that mediate the comparison and choice between an immediate versus a delayed punishment remain largely unexplored. Understanding how the brain represents the costs associated with both the

immediate event and the anticipatory period is a key challenge.

5. **Methodological Rigour for Complex Decisions:** Investigating these nuanced decisions, which are sensitive to subtle contextual factors and internal states, demands highly controlled, standardized experimental approaches. Automated behavioural paradigms (Section 2.6) offer the necessary precision but require careful validation and implementation to yield reliable insights into these complex processes.

The research presented in this thesis was designed specifically to address these critical gaps in the literature. The **primary rationale** is to provide a clear, empirical test of preference between immediate (termed 'advanced' in our protocol) and delayed punishment under highly controlled conditions, thereby clarifying the conflicting findings regarding the temporal processing of aversive outcomes.

Specifically, this study aims to contribute by:

- **Directly Comparing Punishment Timings:** By employing a novel automated T-maze paradigm where mice choose between two paths offering identical, immediate rewards but differing only in the timing of a guaranteed punishment (advanced vs. delayed bright light exposure), this study directly isolates the effect of punishment temporality, addressing Gaps 1 and 2.
- **Providing Behavioural Evidence for Anticipatory Cost:** The observed robust preference for the advanced punishment path, despite significantly increased decision latencies and trial durations, provides strong behavioural evidence consistent with the hypothesis that the cost of anticipating the delayed punishment outweighs the cost of the immediate punishment under these conditions (addressing Gap 3). The dissociation between choice preference and decision time highlights the conflict involved.
- **Utilizing a Validated Automated System:** The development and use of a custom-designed, validated automated T-maze with precise sensor-based tracking, automated door control, and consistent stimulus/reward delivery ensures the methodological rigor required to reliably investigate this complex decision process

(addressing Gap 5).

- **Establishing a Foundation for Neural Investigation:** By providing a robust behavioural characterization of choice patterns and temporal dynamics in this specific temporal punishment conflict paradigm, this work establishes a crucial foundation for future studies aimed at dissecting the underlying neural circuit mechanisms (e.g., using optogenetics, chemogenetics, or in vivo recording) involved in evaluating and choosing between temporally distinct punishments (setting the stage to address Gap 4)

The use of an automated, customizable behavioural platform opens doors for future experiments integrating pharmacological manipulations, optogenetics, or circuit-level recordings, thereby laying a scalable foundation for neurobiological investigation into decision-making

This thesis seeks to resolve existing ambiguities regarding the temporal processing of aversion, provide behavioural evidence for the significant impact of anticipatory states on choice, and offer a reliable paradigm for future neurobiological explorations. Understanding these fundamental decision processes has potential implications for translational research aimed at addressing maladaptive choices observed in various psychiatric and neurological disorders, where the evaluation of future consequences is often perturbed.

CHAPTER 3: GENESIS OF HYPOTHESIS & OBJECTIVES

3.1 Hypothesis and Aims

Based on the theoretical framework suggesting a significant psychological cost associated with anticipating aversive events and preliminary observations from the data presented herein, we hypothesize that:

Hypothesis: Mice will exhibit a preference for the pathway leading to an immediate (advanced) punishment over a pathway leading to a delayed punishment, even when the magnitude of punishment and the associated reward are identical across paths. This preference suggests that the subjective cost of anticipating the delayed punishment outweighs the immediate cost of the advanced punishment.

3.2 Objectives

1. **Develop and Validate an Automated T-Maze:** Construct and functionally validate an automated T-maze system capable of precisely controlling stimulus presentation (visual cues/punishment), reward delivery, path access, and recording behavioural choices and timing parameters in mice.
2. **Assess Baseline Spatial Preference:** Determine if mice exhibit any inherent side bias in the apparatus during habituation, prior to the introduction of reward or punishment contingencies.
3. **Evaluate Choice Preference under Temporal Punishment Conflict:** Quantify the selection bias of mice when choosing between two paths offering equal rewards but associated with either an immediate (advanced) or a delayed punishment.

Analyse Temporal Dynamics of Decision-Making: Measure and compare the decision latency (time taken at the choice point) and total trial duration associated with choices leading to advanced versus delayed punishment

CHAPTER 4: METHODS & MATERIALS

This chapter details the experimental subjects, the design and operation of the custom-built automated T-maze apparatus, the behavioural procedures implemented, and the methods used for data acquisition and statistical analysis. All procedures were conducted in accordance with Institutional Animal Ethics Committee of the Indian Institute of Science.

4.1 Subjects

Subjects were (N=12 mice) adult male Adult C57BL/6J wild-type (WT) male and female mice were used in accordance with a protocol approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee of the Indian Institute of Science. The mice were acclimatized to the CNS animal facility for 1-2 weeks. The mice were group housed in a standard size Plexiglas cage and were maintained under constant and standard temperature (23°C) and humidity (50%) on a 12:12h light/dark cycle. Both groups of mice were freely allowed to explore the experimenter's gloved hands for 10 minutes across 4 days before the behavioural tests. Cages were brought to the behavioural room one hour before the experimental procedure. There were 2 groups of mice, **Group A** with the advanced punishment on the right arm and delayed on the left side, and **Group B** with the advanced punishment on the left arm and delayed on the right side. Both groups consisted of an equal ratio of males and females.

Automated T-Maze Apparatus

4.2 Apparatus: The Automated T-Maze

To precisely investigate decision-making under the punishment conflict, a custom-designed automated T-maze apparatus was developed and implemented. The automation was designed to ensure consistent trial structure, minimize experimenter intervention, allow for precise control over stimuli and outcomes, and enable high-resolution behavioural data acquisition.

Figure 1: IR illuminated image the Automated T-maze setup

4.2.1 General Design and Construction

The core structure of the apparatus was based on a standard T-maze design but modified to incorporate a continuous loop, enabling mice to return to the starting position after completing a choice without requiring experimenter handling. The maze was constructed from wood, which was treated with multiple coats of varnish to enhance durability and facilitate cleaning between subjects and sessions. The overall dimensions of the maze structure were 90 cm (length) x 30 cm (width) x 25 cm (height), with internal corridor widths of 10 cm.

4.2.2 Automation Components

The apparatus integrated several electronic components controlled by a central microcontroller unit:

- **Animal Tracking Sensors:** Five Infrared (IR) proximity sensors were strategically positioned to monitor the animal's location within key Regions of Interest (ROIs) and trigger task events. These sensors were connected to the microcontroller's analog input pins configured for digital reading:

- IRS1 (Pin A0): Located at the start arm entry (ROI1), detecting trial initiation.
 - IRS2 (Pin A1): Positioned at the entrance to the left choice arm (ROI2), registering commitment to this path.
 - IRS3 (Pin A3): Positioned at the entrance to the right choice arm (ROI3), registering commitment to this path.
 - IRS4 (Pin A2): Located near the end/exit of the left choice arm (ROI4), signalling potential reward zone entry or trial segment completion.
 - IRS5 (Pin A4): Located near the end/exit of the right choice arm (ROI5), serving a similar function for the alternative path.
- **Access Control Actuators (Doors):** Four servo motors (Left Door 1, Left Door 2, Right Door 1, Right Door 2) controlled custom-built guillotine doors. These doors regulated access to the choice arms and goal zones, managed using the standard Arduino Servo library for precise positional control based on task logic and animal location.
 - **Outcome Delivery Actuators (Reward):** Two solenoid valves (Connected to digital pins 11 and 10) were used to dispense controlled volumes of liquid reward 10% sucrose solution, into reward receptacles located in the goal zones of the respective choice arms. Activation was triggered by the microcontroller upon the animal making a choice and entering the corresponding arm.
 - **Stimulus Delivery Actuators (Punishment/Cues):** Four LED panels were employed (Connected to digital pins 13, 12, 8, 9; corresponding to Left LED 1, Left LED 2, Right LED 1, Right LED 2, respectively), with two panels associated with each choice arm. Connected to Pulse-Width Modulation (PWM) capable pins, the timing, duration, and intensity of illumination could be precisely controlled by the software. In this study, these LEDs served as the precisely controlled aversive light stimuli contingent upon arm choice and timing parameters.
 - **Control Unit:** An Arduino-compatible microcontroller Arduino Mega ADK served as the central processing unit, executing the custom control logic and managing all sensor inputs and actuator outputs.

4.2.3 System Integration and Control Logic

The microcontroller continuously monitored the state of the IR sensors. Custom control software, executed on the microcontroller, implemented a state-based logic that governed the progression of each behavioural trial based on the sequence and timing of sensor activations. The system automated the entire trial sequence, ensuring consistency. The core logic proceeded as follows

1. **Trial Initiation:** A trial began when the mouse activated IRS1 in ROI1. The system registered the trial start (start_trial flag set), activated the relevant LED panels in the choice arms (as per experimental phase conditions), and opened both entry doors (LD1 and RD1).
2. **Choice Registration:** The system monitored IRS2 (ROI2) and IRS3 (ROI3). Activation of IRS2 indicated a choice for the left path (ROI2 flag, LRP flag set), while activation of IRS3 indicated a choice for the right path (ROI3 flag, RRP flag set). Upon choice registration, both entry doors (LD1, RD1) were closed to prevent retracing.
3. **Consequence Delivery:** Contingent on the choice (IRS2 vs. IRS3 activation), the corresponding reward solenoid was activated to deliver the liquid reward. The LED panels were controlled according to the punishment contingency associated with the chosen arm (advanced vs. delayed timing). Simultaneously, the exit door for the chosen arm (LD2 or RD2) was opened.
4. **Trial Completion & Reset:** Activation of the exit sensor in the chosen arm (IRS4 in ROI4 or IRS5 in ROI5) signaled the end of the choice segment. This triggered the closure of the corresponding exit door (LD2 or RD2), deactivation of the LEDs, and setting of a trial reset flag (reset_trial = True). The reset routine returned all state flags to false and managed doors for inter-trial positioning, returning the system to await the next IRS1 trigger for a new trial.

4.3 Experimental Procedure

4.3.1 Animal Handling and Habituation

Prior to task-specific training or testing, mice underwent a two-day habituation period within the automated T-maze apparatus. The primary goals were to acclimatize the animals to the maze environment and assess any baseline spatial or arm preference in the absence of programmed rewards or punishments. During these sessions, mice were allowed to freely explore the entire apparatus for 15 minutes per day. Behaviour (arm entries) was recorded automatically via the IR sensors to quantify baseline exploration patterns.

4.3.2 Behavioural Task: Advanced vs. Delayed Punishment

Following habituation, mice (N=12) were tested in the decision-making task. Each trial involved a choice between the left and right arms of the T-maze. Both arms offered an equal magnitude of liquid reward delivered immediately upon entry (500µl). The critical manipulation was the timing of the aversive punishment (bright light exposure via LED panels)

Group A :

- **Advanced Punishment Path:** Upon entry into this arm, IRS 3 detects the decision, and the bright light stimulus is delivered immediately.
- **Delayed Punishment Path:** Upon entry into this arm, IRS 2 detects the decision, and the bright light stimulus is delivered immediately.

Group B:

- **Advanced Punishment Path:** Upon entry into this arm, IRS 2 detects the decision, and the bright light stimulus is delivered immediately.
- **Delayed Punishment Path:** Upon entry into this arm, IRS 3 detects the decision, and the bright light stimulus is delivered immediately.

4.3.3 Definition of Behavioural Measures

Data logged from the IR sensors allowed for the calculation of the following primary behavioural measures for each mouse:

- **Arm Choice Percentage:** The number of trials in which the advanced punishment path was chosen, divided by the total number of completed trials, expressed as a percentage. The percentage choice for the delayed path was calculated accordingly. Choice was determined by the first activation of either IRS2 or IRS3 following an IRS1 trigger.
- **Decision Latency (seconds):** Calculated as the time elapsed between the activation of the trial initiation sensor (IRS1) and the activation of either choice arm entry sensor (IRS2 or IRS3). This measure reflects the time taken at the choice point.
- **Trial Duration (seconds):** Defined as the total time elapsed after activating IRS 1 till the activation of IRS 4 or IRS 5 sensor. This reflects the overall time commitment per trial cycle.

4.3.4 Experimental Workflow

The experimental protocol commenced following adequate habituation and pre-training of the subjects.

4.3.4.1 Phase 1: Habituation (2 days)

Subjects underwent a 2-day habituation period to acclimatize them to the experimental apparatus and testing environment. During this phase, mice were allowed to freely explore the Automated T-maze for 15 minutes per day. No rewards or punishments were delivered during habituation to minimize stress and ensure familiarization with the maze cues in a neutral context.

4.3.4.2 Phase 2: Forced Choice Trials (FCT) / Pre-training (2 days)

Following habituation, subjects proceeded to a 2-day forced-choice trial phase. The objective of this phase was to ensure that mice acquired knowledge of both choice alternatives (i.e., maze arms) and their associated reward. On each trial, one arm of the maze was blocked, compelling the mouse to enter the alternate, open arm where a 10% sucrose solution was available. Each arm was presented as the forced choice for an duration of 8 minutes per arm. This procedure was counterbalanced across subjects. Punishment (LED light exposure) was not administered during this phase.

Figure 2: Flowchart depicting Experimental Workflow

4.3.4.3 Phase 3: Free Choice Baseline / Side Bias Assessment (2 Days)

Upon completion of FCTs, a free-choice baseline assessment was conducted. During this session, lasting 15 minutes per mouse, subjects were allowed to freely choose between

both maze arms, both of which contained the 10% sucrose reward. No punishment was delivered. Choice data from this phase were analysed to ascertain any inherent side biases prior to the introduction of the punishment contingency.

4.3.4.4 Phase 4: Experimental Phase (Punishment Conflict Task) (5 days)

The final experimental phase spanned 5 consecutive days. Each mouse was tested for one 15-minute session per day. In this phase, choices were associated with both reward (10% sucrose in the chosen arm) and punishment. Choice behaviour, decision latencies, and were recorded for subsequent analysis.

4.4 Data Acquisition and Analysis

4.4.1 Data Logging

Throughout all behavioural sessions, including habituation and experimental testing phases, precise temporal data corresponding to the activation of each infrared (IR) sensor (designated IRS1 through IRS5) were automatically acquired and recorded by the embedded microcontroller unit. This continuous stream of timestamped sensor events was transmitted in real-time to a dedicated data acquisition computer via a serial communication interface, operating at a baud rate of 9600 bps.

The receiving computer executed custom-developed data logging software, scripted in Python, linked to PLX-DQA and CSV files. This software was responsible for collecting the incoming serial data stream, associating timestamps with specific sensor events, and potentially integrating with PLX-DAQ (Plexon Data Acquisition system) for synchronised recording if applicable, as seen in Figure 3. All processed event data, including sensor identification and corresponding activation timestamps, were systematically logged and saved in comma-separated value (CSV) format for persistent storage.

This automated data logging methodology enabled continuous, real-time monitoring of the animal's position and progression through the apparatus by tracking the sequence and timing of IR beam breaks. The comprehensive timestamp data thus collected served as the

primary raw dataset for all subsequent offline extraction of behavioural measures and statistical analysis.

Figure 3 : PLX-DQA setup for tracking and logging mice behaviour

4.4.2 Statistical Methods

All statistical analyses were performed using custom Python scripts and GraphPad Prism. Data were tested for normality and homogeneity of variance where appropriate.

- **Habituation Data:** Baseline arm preference was analysed using a two-way repeated measures Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with 'Arm' (Left vs. Right) and 'Day' (Day 1 vs. Day 2) as within-subject factors.
- **Decision-Making Data:** Choices and temporal measures during the punishment task were analysed using paired t-tests to compare performance related to the Advanced Punishment path versus the Delayed Punishment path within each subject. Measures compared included: percentage arm choice, mean decision latency per chosen path type, and mean trial duration per chosen path type.

Effect sizes for significant findings from t-tests were estimated using R-squared (partial eta-squared derived from t-statistic). All statistical tests used an alpha level of $p < 0.05$ for determining significance.

CHAPTER 5: RESULTS

Part A: Development and Implementation of an Automated T-Maze Assay

To facilitate the precise execution and objective measurement of behavioural parameters within the decision-making task, a custom-designed automated T-maze apparatus was developed and implemented. Automation was crucial for ensuring consistent trial structure, accurate timing of stimuli and rewards, minimising experimenter handling or intervention during trials, and enabling high-resolution data acquisition and real-time tracking. The system integrated sensors for detecting the animal's position, actuators for controlling access and delivering outcomes, and a central microcontroller unit for orchestrating task events and logging data.

5.1 Apparatus Design and Dimensions

The assay was built out of wood. The wood was varnished several times to preserve the quality over time and make the assay more sturdy. The starting design was of a normal T-Maze, which was modified in such a way that the rodent is allowed to come back to the starting point without taking the same path as before, and also without human intervention. The dimensions for the assay were as stated in Figure 4 (A and B).

Figure 4 (A and B): Automated T-Maze Apparatus Design.

Schematic diagrams A and B presenting the key dimensions (in centimetres) of the custom-constructed automated T-maze apparatus used for the behavioural experiments. The diagram illustrates the overall length (90cm), width (30cm), height (25cm), arm width (10cm), and central alley dimensions critical for standardising the testing environment. Construction utilised varnished wood for durability.

5.2 Automated Control, Reward Delivery, and Stimulus Presentation

The core apparatus consisted of a standard T-maze structure but modified to be a continuous loop, allowing the mice to come back to the starting position without any intervention. Animal location and progression through the maze were monitored using five Infrared (IR) proximity sensors positioned at key Regions of Interest (ROIs). These sensors were interfaced with the microcontroller via digital input pins configured on analog inputs:

IRS1 (Pin A0): Located at the entry point of the start arm (ROI1), detecting the initiation of a trial or departure from the starting area.

IRS2 (Pin A1): Positioned at the entrance to the designated 'advanced/delayed stressor' arm (ROI2), registering the animal's commitment to this path.

IRS3 (Pin A3): Positioned at the entrance to the designated 'advanced/delayed stressor' (ROI3), registering commitment to this alternative path.

IRS4 (Pin A2): Located towards the end or exit point of the 'advanced/delayed stressor' arm (ROI4), potentially signalling reward zone entry or initiation of return.

IRS5 (Pin A4): Located towards the end or exit point of the 'advanced/delayed stressor' arm (ROI5), serving a similar function for the alternative path. The sequential activation pattern of these IR sensors provided the basis for determining the animal's choices and calculating various temporal measures like decision latency and trial duration.

A

B

Figure 5 (A and B): Control System Wiring Schematic for the Automated T-Maze. Diagram illustrating the electronic connections between the Arduino MEGA ADK microcontroller unit and peripheral components of the automated T-maze. Inputs shown originate from five Infrared (IR) proximity sensors used for positional tracking (IRS1-5). Outputs control four servo motors actuating automated guillotine doors (Left/Right Door 1 & 2), two solenoid valves for reward delivery (Solenoid Left/Right), and four LED panels for visual stimulation (LED 1/2 Left/Right Arm). Common ground connections are also indicated.

5.4 Control System, Actuation, and Stimulus Delivery

An Arduino-compatible microcontroller served as the central processing unit, executing the custom control logic for the task. This unit managed several output components and executed according to the logic of the code:

- **Automated Doors:** Access to and containment within specific maze sections were controlled by four servo motors connected to digital output pins (Pin 2: left_door1, Pin 6: left_door2, Pin 3: right_door1, Pin 5: right_door2). These motors, controlling guillotine doors, were managed using the standard Arduino Servo library, allowing for precise control over path availability based on the trial phase and animal location.
- **Reward Delivery:** Distinct outcomes were delivered via two solenoid valves connected to digital output pins (Pin 11, Pin 10). Activation of these valves dispensed controlled volumes of liquid reward to the chosen arm, triggered by the microcontroller based on the animal reaching the appropriate ROI.
- **Visual Stimulation/Cueing:** Four LED panels (Pin 13: left_led1, Pin 12: left_led2, Pin 8: right_led1, Pin 9: right_led2), two associated with each choice arm, were connected to Pulse-Width Modulation (PWM) capable digital pins. This allowed for software control over the timing, duration, and intensity of illumination, enabling their use as visual cues or, as implemented in the present study, precisely controlled aversive light stimuli contingent upon arm choice and timing parameters.

5.5 Control Logic and Automated Task Execution

The behavioural task was managed by custom control software executed on the microcontroller, implementing a state-based logic contingent upon the animal's interaction with the apparatus, as monitored by the strategically placed Infrared (IR) sensors. The system was designed to automate the entire trial sequence, from initiation through choice, outcome delivery, and reset, ensuring consistency across trials and subjects.

Trial Initiation Sequence: A trial sequence started when the subject, positioned in the start arm, activated the first IR sensor (IRS1) at the entry Region of Interest (ROI1). This event triggered several immediate actions: the system registered the trial start (setting an internal start_trial flag to true), activated the relevant LED panels within the choice arms (providing visual cues or stimuli as per the experimental phase), and simultaneously opened the entry doors to both choice arms (Left Door 1 - LD1, and Right Door 1 - RD1), permitting the animal to advance towards the choice point.

Choice Registration and Consequence Delivery: Following trial initiation, the system monitored the IR sensors located at the entrance of the choice arms (IRS2 at ROI2 for the Delayed Punishment Path [DPP]; IRS3 at ROI3 also for the Advanced Punishment Path [APP]). These reward paths alternate alternating advanced punishment depending on the group and cohort used. Activation of either sensor signified the animal's choice:

- **Delayed Punishment Path Choice (ROI2 Activation):** Upon detection by IRS2, the system registered the selection of the RP (set flags ROI 2 = True, DPP = True). Concurrently, the entry doors (LD1 and RD1) were closed to prevent retracing. The solenoid valve was immediately activated to dispense the appropriate reward into the goal zone of that arm. Finally, the exit door for the high-reward arm (Left Door 2 - LD2) was opened, allowing the animal to proceed after potential reward consumption.
- **Advanced Punishment Path Choice (ROI3 Activation):** Alternatively, if IRS3 was activated, the system registered the selection of the APP (setting flags ROI 3 = True, APP = True), closed the entry doors (LD1 and RD1), triggered the reward

solenoid, and opened the corresponding exit door for that arm (Right Door 2 - RD2).

- This is altered for each cohort. Meaning, different cohorts had inverted APP and DPP so that judgment for any side biases could be made.

Trial Completion and System Reset: The completion of a trial segment was registered by the activation of IR sensors located towards the end of the chosen goal arm (IRS4 at ROI4 for DPP; IRS5 at ROI5 for APP), typically after reward consumption.

- **DPP Completion (ROI4 Activation):** Detection by IRS4 triggered the closure of the associated exit door (LD2), the deactivation of the LED panels, and the setting of an internal flag (`reset_trial = True`) to initiate the trial reset sequence.
- **APP Completion (ROI5 Activation):** Similarly, detection by IRS5 resulted in the closure of the corresponding exit door (RD2), deactivation of the LEDs, and setting of the `reset_trial` flag.

The activation of the `reset_trial` flag signaled the end of the current trial's active phase. The control software then executed a reset routine: all state flags were returned to their initial 'false' values (`start_trial = False`, `reset_trial = False`), relevant doors were managed for inter-trial positioning (ensuring choice arm entry doors LD1/RD1 remained closed while potentially opening a return path, depending on overall maze configuration), and the system returned to its initial state, awaiting the next activation of IRS1 (ROI1) to begin a new trial.

Throughout this sequence, the precise timestamps of each IR sensor activation were recorded and transmitted via serial communication to an external computer, enabling accurate offline analysis of the animal's choices, decision latencies, and other temporal aspects of performance within the framework of this automated control logic.

Figure 6: Simplified code logic for the Automated T-Maze

5.6 System Integration and Data Acquisition

The microcontroller continuously monitored the inputs from the IR sensors. Based on the sequence and timing of sensor triggers, the embedded control script executed the pre-programmed task logic, operating the servo doors, LED panels, and solenoid valves by the experimental protocol (e.g., opening start door, detecting arm choice via IRS2/IRS3, closing entry door, activating arm-specific LEDs and/or rewards, detecting exit via IRS4/IRS5, opening return doors).

Crucial behavioural event data, such as the timestamps corresponding to the activation of each IR sensor, were transmitted from the microcontroller to a connected computer via serial communication established at a baud rate of 9600. This data stream facilitated automated, real-time logging, allowing for subsequent offline analysis of choice percentages, decision latencies (time between ROI1 trigger and ROI2/ROI3 trigger), and

total trial durations (time between consecutive ROI1 triggers or other defined start/end points) with high temporal accuracy.

We were able to successfully develop and integrate this automated T-maze system. This provides a robust platform for investigating complex decision-making processes in rodents. It ensured standardised trial execution, precise control over environmental stimuli and reinforcement schedules, and objective, high-resolution recording of behavioural choices and their temporal dynamics, thereby enhancing the reliability and validity of the experimental findings.

Part B: Behavioural Assessment of Decision-Making

5.7 Baseline Spatial Preference Assessment (Habituation Phase)

Before introducing any task contingencies (reward or punishment), the baseline exploratory behaviour and potential spatial preferences of the mice (N=12) were assessed during a two-day habituation period within the Automated T-maze. During these sessions, animals were allowed to freely explore the apparatus without the presence of rewards or aversive stimuli in either arm. The primary goal was to determine if there existed any inherent bias towards selecting the left or right arm of the maze. The choice behaviour was analysed using a 2-way ANOVA. This was done between 2 groups (A and B). This analysis aimed at determining any inherent bias that the mice would have.

Arm selection percentage was recorded across both habituation days. Visual representation of these data (Figure 7) suggests that exploration was distributed approximately equally between the two arms across both days. The mean choice percentages for both the left and right arms remained close to the 50% chance level on Day 1 (Left Arm \approx 49.0%; Right Arm \approx 50.9%) and Day 2 (Left Arm \approx 53.7%; Right Arm \approx 46.3%), with considerable overlap in individual animal data points.

To evaluate potential side preferences and any changes across the habituation period, a two-way repeated measures ANOVA was conducted with 'Arm' (Left vs. Right) and 'Day' (Day 1 vs. Day 2) as within-subject factors. The analysis revealed no significant main effect of 'Arm' ($F(1, 11) = 0.237, p = 0.636$), indicating that, overall, mice did not display a preference for one arm over the other. Similarly, there was no significant main effect of 'Day' ($F(1, 11) = 0.021, p = 0.339$), suggesting that the general pattern of arm exploration did not significantly differ between the two habituation days. Critically, the interaction between 'Arm' and 'Day' was also non-significant ($F(1, 11) = 1.468, p = 0.251$), demonstrating that choice patterns for the arms remained consistent across both days.

Further confirmation of the lack of bias was obtained from post-hoc Tukey's multiple comparisons tests, which showed no significant differences in choice percentage between the left and right arms on either Day 1 ($p = 0.984$) or Day 2 ($p = 0.548$), nor any significant changes in preference for a specific arm between Day 1 and Day 2 (Left arm: $p = 0.823$; Right arm: $p = 0.830$)

Collectively, these findings from the habituation phase strongly indicate the absence of any pre-existing side bias in arm selection among the subjects or inherent environmental cues favouring one side of the T-maze apparatus..

Figure 7: Baseline Arm Preference During Habituation. Mean (\pm SEM) percentage of entries into the left versus right arm of the T-maze during two days of free exploration habituation by mice ($N=12$). Data for Day 1 are represented by black bars, and Day 2 by red bars. Individual subject data points are overlaid. A two-way repeated measures ANOVA revealed no significant main effects of Arm or Day, nor a significant interaction (all $p > 0.25$), indicating no inherent side bias or change in exploration pattern across days. Non-significant comparisons are denoted by 'ns'

5.8 Mice Training Confirmation:

To assess whether mice learned the procedural aspects of the Automated T-maze task and improved their efficiency over time, the duration taken to complete forced choice trials was analysed across two consecutive days of forced choice training. Figure 8 presents the trial duration data for each individual mouse (N=12) on Day 1 (D1) and Day 2 (D2).

Figure 8: Reduction in Forced Choice Trial Duration Across Consecutive Days Suggests Task Learning. Box plots illustrate the distribution of trial durations for each mouse (M1-M12) during forced choice trials on Day 1 (D1) and Day 2 (D2) of the Forced Choice Trials. Each box represents the interquartile range (IQR), with the internal line indicating the median and the red dashed line indicating the mean. Whiskers extend to 1.5x IQR, and circles denote outliers. A general trend towards decreased trial duration from D1 to D2 is observable for most subjects, indicative of learning and increased efficiency in navigating the maze and completing trials.

Visual inspection of the box plots reveals a general trend towards a reduction in trial duration from D1 to D2 for a majority of the subjects. For instance, mice M1, M2, M4, M5, M6, M7, M8, M9, M10, M11, and M12 typically exhibited lower median and mean trial durations on D2 compared to D1. This decrease is indicative of task learning, as animals became more proficient at navigating the maze, locating the reward, and progressing through the trial sequence.

While considerable inter-individual variability in overall speed was noted, and some mice (e.g., M3) showed less pronounced changes or minimal improvement between the two days, the predominant pattern supports the interpretation of learning and adaptation to the task contingencies. The presence of outliers in several sessions, representing trials of exceptionally long duration, is common in such behavioural assays but did not obscure the overall trend of decreasing central tendencies in trial duration for most animals.

5.9 Choice Preference Between Advanced vs. Delayed Punishment

The primary measure to assess the impact of punishment timing on decision-making was the choice preference exhibited by the mice (N=12) in the T-maze. Mice chose between a path leading to an immediate, advanced punishment and a path leading to a delayed punishment, with equal rewards available in both goal arms.

Visual representation of the choice data (Figure 9) indicates a marked preference for the path associated with advanced punishment. The mean percentage of choices directed towards the advanced punishment arm (Mean = 65.54%) was substantially higher than the percentage of choices directed towards the delayed punishment arm (Mean = 34.46%). Individual data points overlaid on the bars show that this preference was highly consistent across nearly all subjects.

To statistically evaluate this observed preference, the percentage of choices for the advanced path versus the delayed path for each mouse was compared using a paired t-test. The analysis revealed a highly significant difference between the selection of the two paths ($t(11) = 11.30, p < 0.0001$). Mice selected the advanced punishment path significantly more often than the delayed punishment path.

The magnitude of this preference was substantial. On average, mice chose the advanced punishment path 31.08 percentage points more frequently than the delayed punishment path (95% Confidence Interval of the difference: 25.03% to 37.14%; SEM of differences =

2.751). Furthermore, the effect size for this difference was large, as indicated by an R^2 value of 0.9207, suggesting that the timing of the punishment accounted for approximately 92% of the variance in choice preference within this paired comparison

This provides compelling evidence that under the current experimental conditions, mice strongly prefer to face an immediate (advanced) punishment rather than a delayed one when rewards are otherwise equal. This robust preference was evident both in the average choice percentages and the highly significant statistical comparison across all subjects.

Figure 9: Choice Preference Between Paths Leading to Advanced versus Delayed Punishment. Mean (\pm SEM) percentage of trials in which mice ($N=12$) selected the path leading to advanced (immediate) punishment (red bar) compared to the path leading to delayed punishment (black bar). Individual subject data points are shown. A paired t-test indicated a highly significant preference for the advanced punishment path ($t(11) = 11.30$, **** $p < 0.0001$), demonstrating that mice chose to confront the aversive stimulus immediately rather than postpone it.

5.10 Analysis of Decision Latency at Choice Point

To understand the cognitive processing underlying the choice behaviour, the decision latency was analysed. Decision latency was defined as the time elapsed between the mouse leaving the start area of the Automated T-maze and fully committing to entering one of the choice arms (left or right). This measure can reflect factors such as hesitation, conflict, or deliberation time at the choice point. The decision latencies were compared specifically based on the path ultimately chosen in each trial – the one leading to advanced punishment or the one leading to delayed punishment.

Visual inspection of the data, presented in Figure 10, reveals a clear difference in decision times contingent upon the chosen path. Mice consistently took longer to make a decision when selecting the path associated with advanced punishment compared to when selecting the path associated with delayed punishment. The mean decision time preceding entry into the advanced punishment arm was approximately 480.8 seconds, whereas the mean decision time preceding entry into the delayed punishment arm was approximately 269.2 seconds. Individual subject data points illustrate this trend across the cohort.

A paired t-test was employed to statistically compare the mean decision latency for choices leading to advanced versus delayed punishment within each subject ($N=12$). The analysis confirmed a highly significant difference between the two conditions ($t(11) = 8.006$, $p < 0.0001$).

Quantitatively, mice took substantially longer, by an average of 211.6 seconds, to commit to the advanced punishment arm compared to the delayed punishment arm (95% Confidence Interval for the difference: 153.4 to 269.7 seconds; SEM of differences = 26.43 seconds). This represents a considerable increase in deliberation time when choosing the path with the imminent aversive stimulus. The effect size for this difference in decision latency was very large ($R^2 = 0.8535$), indicating that the chosen punishment timing condition accounted for approximately 85% of the variance in decision time within this paired analysis.

Despite the established preference for the advanced punishment path (as detailed previously), the act of choosing this path was associated with significantly increased

decision latencies. This suggests that while ultimately preferred, the prospect of immediate punishment induced greater hesitation or required more prolonged processing at the point of decision compared to choosing the delayed punishment alternative

Figure 10: Decision Latency as a Function of Chosen Punishment Path. Mean (\pm SEM) decision time, measured in seconds from trial initiation to arm entry, for mice ($N=12$) contingent upon their choice of the advanced punishment path (red bar) or the delayed punishment path (black bar). Individual subject data points are displayed. A paired t-test revealed that decision latency was significantly longer when choosing the preferred advanced punishment path compared to the delayed path ($t(11) = 8.006$, **** $p < 0.0001$), suggesting increased deliberation or conflict before committing to the immediately punished route.

5.11 Analysis of Total Trial Duration

To evaluate the overall time commitment associated with pursuing either the advanced or delayed punishment path, the total trial duration was analysed. This duration encompassed the entire sequence from the initiation of a trial until its completion (e.g., concluding with

reward retrieval and entry into the return arm). Differences in trial duration can reflect cumulative effects of start latency, decision time, and subsequent travel or activity time within the maze arm and goal zone.

Examination of the trial duration data, presented graphically in Figure 11, revealed substantial differences depending on the choice made by the mice. Trials in which the animal selected the arm leading to advanced punishment consistently required more time to complete compared to trials where the delayed punishment arm was selected. The average duration for trials involving the advanced punishment path reached approximately 1299.7 seconds (\pm [Insert SEM if calculated]), markedly longer than the average duration of approximately 680.3 seconds (\pm [Insert SEM if calculated]) for trials involving the delayed punishment path. This pattern of prolonged duration for advanced punishment trials was generally consistent across individual animals, as indicated by the data points in the figure.

Statistical analysis using a paired t-test ($N=12$) confirmed that the observed difference in total trial duration between the two conditions was highly significant ($t(11) = 7.814$, $p < 0.0001$)

Quantifying this effect, trials culminating in the choice of the advanced punishment path required, on average, an additional 619.4 seconds to complete compared to those involving the delayed punishment path (95% Confidence Interval for the mean difference: 444.9 to 793.9 seconds; SEM of differences = 79.27 seconds). This substantial difference highlights a major divergence in the overall time investment based on the punishment timing contingency chosen. The magnitude of this effect was further underscored by a very large effect size ($R^2 = 0.8473$), indicating that the choice of punishment timing strongly dictated the total time required to complete a trial.

Selecting the path leading to advanced punishment, while representing the preferred strategy based on choice percentage, incurred a significant cost in terms of overall trial duration. This extended duration likely reflects, in large part, the increased decision latency observed for these same trials, demonstrating a clear temporal trade-off associated with the animals' strategy to confront punishment immediately rather than postpone it.

Figure 11: Total Trial Duration as a Function of Chosen Punishment Path. Mean (\pm SEM) total time, in seconds, required for mice ($N=12$) to complete a trial, compared between trials where the advanced punishment path was selected (red bar) and trials where the delayed punishment path was selected (black bar). Individual subject data points are presented. A paired t-test demonstrated that total trial duration was significantly longer for trials involving the choice of the advanced punishment path ($t(11) = 7.814$, **** $p < 0.0001$), likely reflecting the increased decision latency associated with this choice.

CHAPTER 6: DISCUSSION

The primary objective of this study was to investigate how the temporal proximity of an unavoidable aversive event influences decision-making in mice, utilising a purpose-built automated T-maze designed for precise control and measurement. Our results present a compelling, counterintuitive behavioural profile: mice consistently and robustly preferred the pathway associated with an immediate (advanced) punishment over one leading to an identical, but delayed, punishment. Surprisingly, this clear preference was paradoxically accompanied by significantly increased decision latencies and overall trial durations for the chosen, immediately punished path. These findings, underscored by initial habituation data confirming the absence of confounding spatial biases, provide significant insights into the cognitive architecture underlying choices made under the duress of impending negative consequences.

6.1 Preference Driven by the Anticipatory Cost of Delay

The unambiguous preference for the advanced punishment pathway constitutes the central finding. Given the identical nature of the punishment across both conditions, this behavioural pattern strongly suggests that the temporal delay itself, or the psychological state it induces, carries a substantial subjective cost. This aligns conceptually with principles of temporal discounting, often studied in the context of rewards, but increasingly recognized as relevant for aversive outcomes. However, our data suggest a nuanced interplay; rather than simply devaluing the delayed punishment, the intervening period appears to impose a significant burden – potentially related to sustained anticipation, uncertainty, or anxiety – which outweighs the immediate impact of the advanced punishment. Consequently, the animals adopt a strategy best characterized as "getting it over with," choosing the immediate negative outcome to circumvent the prolonged negative affective state associated with awaiting the delayed one. The remarkably large effect size for this preference highlights the potency of this temporal manipulation in governing choice.

6.2 The Temporal Paradox: Hesitation Precedes the Preferred, Costly Choice

Contrasting sharply with the decisive preference was the temporal signature of the decision process itself. Mice exhibited significantly longer decision latencies – reflecting time spent deliberating at the choice point – specifically on trials where they selected the preferred advanced punishment path. This is a critical observation, indicating that a strong overall preference does not necessarily translate to rapid or effortless execution. The increased latency implies the presence of significant decision conflict. While the global cost-benefit analysis favoured the immediate punishment route (likely to minimise the integrated cost of anticipation), the imminent prospect of the aversive stimulus created an immediate barrier. Overcoming this aversion, or resolving the conflict between approaching the associated reward and confronting the impending punishment, demanded greater cognitive processing time compared to choosing the delayed path, where the punishment was temporally distant from the choice point. This shows that even a globally "optimal" or preferred choice within a conflict scenario can incur substantial processing costs at the moment of commitment.

6.3 Extended Trial Duration Reflects Cumulative Temporal Costs

The observed increase in decision time is the primary reason for the significantly longer total trial durations when individuals chose options involving delayed punishment. The considerable difference in the total time spent per trial confirms that the chosen strategy significantly influenced the time required. Although other factors may have played a minor role, the extended decision time is the simplest and most probable explanation for most of the increased trial duration. This supports the conclusion that selecting the option with immediate punishment, even when it was the preferred choice, required substantial time throughout the experiment.

6.4 Synthesis: Dissociating Global Preference from Local Processing Cost

Collectively, these findings highlight an interesting and important difference between the main factors determining the final choice and the less significant factors affecting the immediate time and mental effort needed to make that choice. The final preference seems to be determined by a complete evaluation of the potential outcomes over the entire trial period, heavily influenced by how strongly the anticipation of a delayed negative event is disliked. This suggests a process where the value assigned to an option prioritises reducing long periods of negative feelings or uncertainty over avoiding immediate discomfort. In contrast, the time taken to make a decision directly reflects the conflict and increased mental effort experienced at the moment of choosing, particularly the difficulty in overcoming the immediate dislike of facing a near-term negative stimulus. This difference shows how complex cost-benefit decisions are, especially when they involve conflicting negative outcomes occurring at different times. It strongly suggests that potentially separate brain processes are involved: one system might assess the overall, long-term emotional consequences (guiding preference), while another manages the immediate physical and mental demands of choosing when facing immediate threats (shown by the decision time). Therefore, the animals' behaviour appears to be a complex strategy designed to minimize the total negative experience throughout the trial. This overall best outcome is achieved even though it requires greater immediate effort and time at the crucial decision point and during the execution of the action that leads to immediate punishment but is ultimately preferred.

**CHAPTER 7:
CONCLUSION & FUTURE
DIRECTIONS**

Conclusion

In summary, through the utilisation of a meticulously validated automated T-maze, we have demonstrated that mice consistently exhibit a preference for immediate over delayed punishment. This central finding strongly suggests that the period of anticipation, or the delay itself, carries a significant subjective cost for the animals. Critically, this preference for immediacy is, paradoxically, associated with an increase in both decision latency and overall trial duration. This latter observation is indicative of heightened conflict and an increased processing cost when the animals are choosing the imminently aversive, yet globally preferred, option.

These results reveal a clear and compelling dissociation between the underlying drivers of the ultimate choice an animal makes and the immediate cognitive and temporal costs associated with the execution of that decision. As such, this work offers a refined behavioural framework for exploring the intricate computations that support adaptive behaviour, particularly when organisms are faced with conflicting temporal costs. The rigorous validation of the apparatus and the careful assessment of baseline behaviour serve to strengthen the interpretation that these nuanced behavioural patterns arise directly and specifically from our experimental manipulation of punishment timing, rather than from other confounding factors.

Implications and Future Direction

The research presented herein furnishes a robust behavioural model for the investigation of decision-making processes when organisms are faced with temporally distinct aversive outcomes. This work complements, and indeed extends, the extensive body of research that has traditionally focused on reward discounting. The clearly demonstrated preference for immediacy of punishment, coupled with the intriguing observation of increased processing time for that preferred option, offers a valuable and somewhat novel platform from which to probe the intricate neural circuits that mediate cost-benefit computations involving punishment, the passage of time, and the resolution of conflict.

Future Directions:

- Key brain regions heavily implicated in processing aversion, monitoring conflict, and temporal evaluation – such as the amygdala, the anterior cingulate cortex, and various prefrontal circuits – stand out as prime candidates for future, more targeted investigation.
- Use directed chemogenetic and optogenetic tools to selectively activate or inhibit specific neural populations.
- Future research could systematically vary the parameters of the punishment itself – its intensity, its duration, the precise length of the delay interval – and also manipulate the magnitude of the rewards on offer.
- Identify the thresholds and precise boundaries of the effects observed and explore the complex interactions that undoubtedly occur between appetitive (reward-seeking) and aversive (threat-avoiding) motivational systems.

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